

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN OUR LIFE

Aitmuratova Perkhon Genjebayevna

Yorova Sayyora Karimovna

Esanova Maftuna Bahadirovna

Samarkand State Medical university Teacher of Foreign Chair

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7627418>

Аннотация: В данной статье речь идет об обучении иностранных языков с учётом требований федерального государственного образовательного стандарта начального общего образования, а также в соответствии с Европейскими стандартами в области изучения иностранных языков. Данная статья поможет учащимся использовать английский язык эффективно, развивать мотивы учебной деятельности, формировать личностный смысл учения и даст детям возможность изучать английский язык с удовольствием. Она развивает коммуникативные умения в основных видах речевой деятельности: аудировании, говорении, чтении и письме, формирует умение общаться на английском языке на элементарном уровне с учётом речевых возможностей и потребностей младших школьников в устной (аудирование и говорение) и письменной (чтение и письмо) формах.

Annotation: Annotation: This article deals with the teaching of foreign languages, taking into account the requirements of the federal state educational standard for primary general education, as well as in accordance with European standards in the field of learning foreign languages. This article will help students to use English effectively, develop motives for learning activities, form a personal meaning of learning and give children the opportunity to learn English with pleasure. It develops communication skills in the main types of speech activity: listening, speaking, reading and writing, forms the ability to communicate in English at an elementary level, taking into account the speech capabilities and needs of younger students in oral (listening and speaking) and written (reading and writing) forms .

Introduction. The historical development of foreign language teaching can also be read from the sequence of methods. The methods of teaching in the ancient languages (Greek and Latin) were first transferred to the so-called newer languages (English and French) introduced in school lessons. With the changing demands on foreign language teaching to teach the “living languages” in such a way that they can be used both in writing and orally outside of school assignments, the methods have changed and are changing too. They often took in and absorb what may previously have been neglected by the previous

methods and responded to current needs of society. They also take into account the latest results from the various related sciences.

German as a foreign language is not to be excluded from this development in foreign language teaching methods. Knowledge of the basics of methods is necessary and useful for teachers. This makes it possible to classify textbooks based on the method on which they are based. Knowledge of methods makes it possible to select the appropriate method (the textbook) or the best possible methodological path for the respective target group, their skills and the given learning objectives (see Jung2001,137).

The term method / methodology is derived from the Greco-Latin word *methodos* / *methodus* and means something like: access / path that leads to a specific goal.

The present work aims to address four most important methods and show their differences and similarities: the grammar - translation method, the audio-lingual / audio-visual method, the communicative-pragmatic-oriented method and the mediating method.

Grammar Translation Method.The grammar translation method was adopted from ancient language teaching (Latin, Greek) and transferred to teaching modern foreign languages. German was presented using the categories of Latin grammar, with many exceptions naturally being listed, the learning of which was then often given great importance in class.

The model of language teaching was the written language of aesthetic literature. The language was understood as a building that is composed of certain building blocks according to logical rules.

Audio-lingual / audio-visual method. According to the universal dictionary Duden, the terms *audiolingual* and *audiovisual* are defined as follows: *audiolingual* [from Latin *audire* = to hear and *lingua* = tongue]: [in language lessons] based on the spoken word; *audiovisual*: audible and visible at the same time. With regard to language lessons, the first case concerns the use of sound devices such as e. Cassette recorders, CD-ROMs, in the second case media such as video recorders, audio courses with textbooks, computers. The AL / AV method grew out of a combination of behavioristic learning theory and linguistic structuralism. In the USA, structuralism had established itself as the linguistic basis of foreign language teaching in the 1940s.

Conclusions.This is understood to be a method that selects principles and elements from closed, strict method concepts and mixes them with one another.

When making the selection, the criteria of applicability and reliability in practice play a central role.

It is accepted that the reasons and deductions for sub-goals and sub-areas of language teaching are inconsistent and sometimes contradict each other (e.g. cognitive justification of language acquisition / exclusive use of imitative forms of exercise or explanation of second language acquisition in analogy to mother tongue acquisition / Use of bilingual explanatory procedures and exercises).

Standards of the mediating method that have developed in particular in foreign language teaching at secondary schools:

- Orientation towards intellectual and formal educational concepts (simple waiter German is sufficient)
- High priority in grammar lessons (ability can only be achieved through knowledge; from example to rule)
- the grammar lessons run in cyclical progressions (from elementary to specific)
- High importance of literature lessons (text analysis / reflection on texts ")
- Orientation towards pragmatic learning goals (understanding in conversations is important)
- Emphasis on dialogical communication (everyday communication)
- Observance of the principle of enlightened monolingualism (understanding must be ensured)
- preference for frontal forms of teaching (the teacher must control the acquisition of skills and knowledge)
- Consideration of forms of instruction that promote the independence of the learner (the learner's own activity must be supported)

Bibliography:

1. Rakhmatova Sunbula Ahmadjonovna, Aytmuratova Perxan Genjibaevna, Normuradova Nasiba Saydullaevna, Rakhimova Nigora Atakulovna, Ibragimova Dilbar Sadulayevna The Teacher's Role in the Effective Organization of the Lesson Process in Foreign Language Дата публикации 2021/3/1 Журнал: Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology
2. Yorova S. K., Khakberdiyeva V. J. K. DOCTOR AND PATIENT //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 1478-1480.
3. Yorova S., Nasimova S. The ways of teaching languages at medical institutions. – 2019.
4. Yorova S. K. The concept "health" in the English lingual culture //Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe: Achievements and Perspectives. – 2017. – С. 58-60.

5. Karimovna Y. S. STRATEGIC METHODS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK MEDICAL DISCOURSES //Thematics Journal of Education. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 5.
6. Aitmuratova Perkhan Genjebayevna THE ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS Дата публикации 2022/11/3 ЖурналWeb of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal Том 3 Номер 11 Страницы 41-45
7. Aytmuratova Perkhan Genjebaevna, Esanova Maftuna Bakhadirovna THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING LATIN IN MEDICAL SCHOOLS Дата публикации 2022/12/17 Журнал Thematics Journal of Education Том 7 Номер 5
8. Maxmudov Z. M., Sharipov B. S. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1028-1033.
9. 2. Mardanovich M. Z. et al. Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 5341-5352.
10. 3. ZAFAR M., BOBUR S., DILMUROD B. O. R. SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL BASIS OF TEACHING THE THEORY OF DECISIONS IN SCHOOL CHEMISTRY //International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 192-196.
11. Karimovna Y. S. COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF A SPECIALIST //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2020. – Т. 8. – №. 4.
12. PROPOSITIVE STRUCTURE AND SYNTACTIC DEVICES OF SPEECH DERIVATION (<https://giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/1378>)Авторы: Kurbanova Raxima Abdullaevna Дата публикации 2022/2/28 Журнал Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal Том10.Номер 2-Страницы 764-768

